

GEOTHERMAL ENERGY POTENTIAL IN SOUTHWESTERN NEW BRUNSWICK

Nadia Mohammadi

Carleton University, Department of Earth Sciences, Ottawa, ON, Canada
University of New Brunswick, Department of Earth Sciences, Fredericton, NB, Canada
Correspondent author email: Nadia.mohammadi@unb.ca

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Abstract

The high heat production (HHP) Mount Douglas Granite has elevated concentrations of K₂O, Rb, LREE, U, and Th in response to high degrees of fractional crystallization. The uraniumiferous granite produces anomalous heat generated by radiogenic decay of unstable isotopes, such as ²³⁸U, ²³²Th, and ⁴⁰K. The average weighted mean radiogenic heat production of the granite assuming a density of 2.61 g/cm³ is 5.9 μW/m³ (14.1 HGU) which is significantly higher than the average of upper continental crust (1.65 μW/m³). The high HGU of the granite supports its assignment to a ‘hot crust’ (>7 HGU) HHP granite and highlights its potential for a local, renewable, sustainable, and clean geothermal energy exploration.

1. Introduction

The Late Devonian Mount Douglas Granite (368 ± 3 Ma (Mohammadi, 2018), located in Southwestern New Brunswick, ~40 km east of the Mount Pleasant W–Mo–Bi and Sn–Zn–Cu–In deposits, forms the eastern part of the Late Silurian to Late Devonian Saint George Batholith (Fig. 1). The intrusion is composed of a suite of metaluminous to peraluminous leucogranitic rocks that apparently evolved from a zoned magma chamber in a three-stage process, resulting in compositionally and chronologically distinct units (Fig. 1), i.e., units Dmd1, Dmd2, and Dmd3 (McLeod, 1990). The radiogenic heat production of the Mount Douglas Granite was examined in this study to determine any potential of Hot Dry Rock (HDR) geothermal resources in this area.

2. Methodology and Results

The radiogenic heat production rates of the units Dmd1, Dmd2, and Dmd3 were calculated using whole-rock geochemical data taken from Mohammadi (2018; laser ablation ICP-MS analyses on fused glass beads produced *in house*) and McLeod (1990) following an equation developed by Rybach (1988):

$$A [\mu\text{W}/\text{m}^3] = 10^{-5} \times \rho [\text{kg}/\text{m}^3] \times (2.56 \times C_{\text{Th}} [\text{ppm}] + 9.52 \times C_{\text{U}} [\text{ppm}] + 3.48 \times C_{\text{K}} [\%])$$

where A is heat production and ρ is density (2.61 g/cm³). The C_U and C_{Th} are the concentrations of U and Th (in ppm), respectively, and C_K is the concentration of K in wt.%. The estimated weighted mean radiogenic heat production of the granite is 4.67, 5.65, and 6.93 (μW/m³) for Dmd1, Dmd2, and Dmd3, respectively (Table 1).

Fig. 1 Geology of the Mount Douglas Granite with units Dmd1, Dmd2, and Dmd3 (modified after McLeod 1990; Mohammadi et al. 2017). Black diamonds are mineral occurrences associated with the Mount Douglas Granite, and compiled from the Metallogenic Map of New Brunswick, NR-7 (2002). The mineral occurrences consist of Sn, W, Mo, Zn, and Bi-bearing greisen and sheeted veins.

Table 1 Weighted mean Th (ppm), U (ppm), and K₂O (wt.%) contents for units Dmd1, Dmd2, and Dmd3 of the Mount Douglas Granite and their radiogenic heat production rates, A (μW/m³).

Unit	Density	Th	U	K ₂ O	A
Dmd1	2610	38.0	6.7	5.2	4.59
Dmd2	2610	40.2	10.1	5.0	5.58
Dmd3	2610	50.1	12.6	4.9	6.85
Upper Continental Crust	-	10.5	2.7	-	1.65

Note: Data for units Dmd1, Dm2, and Dmd3 are from Mohammadi, McFarlane, and Lentz (2019). The average upper continental crust values are from Rudnick and Gao (2003).

3. Discussion

The high radiogenic heat production of the Mount Douglas Granite, accompanied by a high estimated heat flow of 70 mW/m² (Chandra, 1980) is comparable to other locations that have been classified as HHP granites (e.g., Leat et al. 2018; Sun et al. 2015) support the assignment of the granite to a 'hot crust' (>7 HGU) HHP granite and highlights its potential for geothermal energy exploration. This could be a local, renewable and clean energy source associated with deep hot crystalline rocks with temperatures generally higher than 150°C. Such high heat production is expected to result in local heat flow anomalies for the area, although further investigation, such as airborne radiometric surveys, seismic data, and satellite magnetic data, are required.

4. Conclusions

Results obtained from this study demonstrate that the Mount Douglas granitic rocks may have great potential for dry geothermal energy sources; however, surface heat flow, which is a function of radioactive element contents below the continents, the latest thermal event, and the intensity of tectonic activities are important parameters that should be considered when evaluating potential geothermal resources.

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